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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction.....	9
1.1	Scope of the Document.....	9
1.2	Objectives	9
2	PILOT EVALUATION PLANNING.....	11
2.1	Road Infrastructure Monitoring Pilot Use Case (RDP).....	11
2.1.1	Pilot-specific KPIs (RDP).....	11
2.1.2	Target Groups for RDP.....	14
2.2	Railway monitoring and prediction of rail temperature zones and early warnings Pilot Use Case (RWP).....	16
2.2.1	Pilot-specific KPIs (RWP).....	16
2.2.2	Target Groups for RWP.....	18
2.3	General Target Groups (common for both pilots, RDP and RWD).....	21
2.3.1	Service developers	21
2.4	General KPIs Common for Both Pilot Use Cases	22
2.4.1	Important General KPIs	22
2.4.2	Medium Importance KPIs.....	23
3.	PILOT EVALUATION PROTOCOLS	25
3.1	Data Collection Techniques.....	25
3.2	Data Analysis Methods.....	26
3.3	Evaluation Methods and Tools	26
3.4	Cross-relational summary of different elements in pilot evaluation process	27
3.5	Deployment plan.....	31
3.5.1	Planning and preparation	31
3.5.2	Prototype (modules, components) development.....	31
3.5.3	Lab testing	32
3.5.4	User enrolment.....	32
3.5.5	Field test setup	32
3.5.6	Pilot deployment.....	33
3.5.7	Real-world testing.....	33
3.5.8	Feedback collection	33
3.5.9	Data Analysis.....	33
3.5.10	Corrective actions	33
3.5.11	Final evaluation	34

3.6	Description of tests per component (RDP)	34
3.6.1	GNSS In-Vehicle Tracking	35
3.6.2	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)	37
3.6.3	SENTINEL-2 Congestion Detection	38
3.6.4	Additional and Alternative Supporting Detection Methods from EO Sources	40
3.6.5	EGNSS Truck Localisation and Telemetry Tracking	42
3.6.6	Parking Drone Detection Algorithm	43
3.6.7	Drone-Based Congestion Detection Algorithm	45
3.6.8	Extended Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) Calculation	46
3.6.9	RDP Monitoring Application	48
3.6.10	RDP Pilot deployment	49
3.7	Description of tests per component RWP	53
3.7.1	Data Discovery and Processor Job Generation	53
3.7.2	Data Collection and Harmonization	54
3.7.3	Thermal Downscaling	55
3.7.4	Rail Track Temperature Prediction	56
3.7.5	Rail Track Buckling Risk Assessment (UNI)	57
3.7.6	Quality Control and Threshold Exceedance Monitoring	58
3.7.7	RWP Monitoring Application (WebGUI)	60
3.7.8	RWP pilot deployment	62
3.7.9	Pilot deployment scenario	64
4	Conclusions and Next Steps	67
5	References	68

Executive Summary

SPATRA aims at increasing the use of satellite data in land transport by developing two new downstream applications for monitoring and management of rail and road transport and demonstrating them in operational environment. This deliverable D4.1 document provides plans for the field-testing validation of both SPATRA pilot systems, road (RDP) and railway (RWP), that will be conducted within the activities of WP4. It defines testing, integration, and evaluation methodology for use cases in the domains identified for the evaluation of the SPATRA outcomes in both workstreams, Road Infrastructure Monitoring and Railway Monitoring and Prediction of Rail Temperature Zones.

As part of the presented evaluation plans, specific KPIs are established for both pilots to measure success against defined targets. Additionally, the presented evaluation plans identify key target groups for both pilots whose feedback is essential in evaluating both the systems' overall performances usability and impact on end-users. This feedback is also essential for the identification of possible issues.

This deliverable D4.1 also outlines the pilot evaluation protocols that provide a structured approach to assess the pilots' implementations systematically, capturing all relevant data to inform future developments and enhancements. The key components of the presented pilots' evaluation protocols are: techniques for data collection, methods for data analysis and evaluation against defined KPIs, pilot schedule with deployment steps in real-world setting including installation and initial testing, and components/modules tests.

Specifying the Pilots' Plans and Evaluation Protocols, this deliverable D4.1 sets-up the basis for SPATRA pilots' demonstration and evaluation activities, including the integration and final pilot systems implementations, which will be reported in following two deliverables of WP4, D4.2- Integration and Validation Report and D4.3- Pilot Results and Analysis Report.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS, ACRONYMS AND DEFINITIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Definition
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring System
CRUD	Create Read Update Delete
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EO	Earth Observation
GA	Grant Agreement
(G)UI	(Graphical) User Interface
IM	Infrastructure Manager
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LST	Land Surface Temperature
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
ML	Machine Learning
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
MSG	Meteosat Second Generation
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
RDP	Road Pilot use case
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
RTT	Rail Track Temperature
RTBR	Rail Track Buckling Risk
RWP	RailWay monitoring and prediction of rail temperature zones and early warnings Pilot use case
STAC	Spatio-Temporal Asset Catalogue
R ²	Coefficient of Determination
EGNSS	European Global Navigation Satellite System

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. High-level RDP-supporting system architecture and organization, reference from D2.1.....	35
Figure 2. Batrovci-Bajakovo border crossing between Serbia and Croatia after the recent 2018 extension, nominally enabling up to 50% increased throughput capacity (image: CIP Institute of Transportation)	50
Figure 3. Satellite map view of the Batrovci (east/right) - Bajakovo (west/left) crossing	50
Figure 4. A congestion on the Batrovci-Bajakovo crossing (image:AMSS-Serbian National Automobile Club live web camera).....	51
Figure 5. Wider zoomed-out enhanced view of the highway approach to the Batrovci crossing, with the detectable line of waiting trucks marked yellow on the left side, and a monitored parking area of interest on the right side	52
Figure 6. High-level architecture of SPATRA RWP service	53
Figure 7. Track Niš – Prahovo.....	62
Figure 8. Track Niš – Preševo	63
Figure 9. Track Niš – Dimitrovgrad	64
Figure 10. Railway pilot (RWP) scenario.....	65
Figure 11. Schematics of in-situ sensor connection for the SPATRA RWP service	66

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 - RDP End-Users	14
Table 2 – RDP End-User Organisations	15
Table 3 – Infrastructure Managers for RDP	16
Table 4 - RWP End Users.....	19
Table 5 - End-user Organisations	20
Table 6 - Service Developers.....	21
Table 7 - Research and Academia	22
Table 8 - Combined table of all segments in pilot evaluation process (required target group types)	27
Table 9 - Combined table of all segments in pilot evaluation process (optional target group types)	30

1 INTRODUCTION

SPATRA will use satellite data assisted by in-situ data to develop two innovative applications for smart transport and logistics, to solve problems of principal modes of land transport, road and rail:

- SPATRA will provide benefits of **satellite-based logistics and road traffic flow monitoring** by reducing congestion and improving the flow of goods and people.
- A novel **space-based service predicting the risk of rail buckling** based on a space downstream application for estimation of the rail temperature will be developed to support prevention of train derailments induced by track buckling.

The work plan of SPATRA is organized in five highly interacting, incremental, and iterative work packages (WPs), where WP4 addresses validation and evaluation of developed SPATRA technologies. This deliverable D4.1 represent the first deliverable of WP4, namely, the Pilot Plan and Protocol Specification, which outlines how the SPATRA pilots will be demonstrated, validated and evaluated. It will be followed with two more deliverables of WP4, D4.2- Integration and Validation Report (Month 22) and D4.3- Pilot Results and Analysis Report (Month 24).

1.1 Scope of the Document

This deliverable D4.1 reports the work conducted in WP4, and in particular the work done in Task 4.1- Specification of the use cases for testing and validation methodology as well as the work done in Task 4.2- Configure and establish SPATRA pilots, which refers to the design of a comprehensive configuration process to establish SPATRA pilots. The part of the work of Task 4.2 that refers to the installation of equipment and related activities such as training will be reported in future deliverable D4.2-Integration and Validation report (Month 22). The process of getting permissions for pilots' demonstration and evaluation activities is also part of Task 4.2 that will be documented in future deliverable D4.3 - Pilot Results and Analysis Report (Month 24).

This deliverable D4.1 report describes the scenarios selected for the field trials and pilot deployment for both SPATRA work streams, road and rail, together with the evaluation methodology, including relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs); those are based on the evolved use cases provided by WP1. This deliverable D4.1 outlines the plan and protocol for executing the pilots of road and rail work streams with stakeholders NELT and Serbian Railway Infrastructure respectively. It includes details such as the scope, timeline, resources required, and success criteria.

1.2 Objectives

The main goal of SPATRA WP4 is to define, deploy and evaluate two pilot services, so as to assess the feasibility and applicability of the techniques, procedures and functions developed during the project lifetime. The objective is to test the developments coming from WP3 in real environments, with real users, facing all the constraints and limitations that a complex environment can pose in these kinds of trials. In order to reach the aforementioned goals, WP4 particularly tackles the following objectives.

- O4.1 Define testing, integration, and evaluation methodology for use cases in the domain identified for the evaluation of the SPATRA outcomes (rail and road)

- O4.2 Deploy infrastructure, hardware and resources for emulation and demonstration of the developed satellite-based interfaces, algorithms, hardware and software
- O4.3 Implementation and integration of modules from WP3 and tasks into the working solutions.
- O4.4 Execution of the testing and validation processes to assess the resilience and performance of the developed solutions.

2 PILOT EVALUATION PLANNING

The pilots' evaluation planning focuses on systematically assessing the effectiveness and performance of the technologies and systems implemented in the Road and Rail Infrastructure Monitoring Pilots.

As part of the evaluation plan, specific KPIs are established to measure success against defined targets. Additionally, the plan identifies key target groups whose feedback is essential in evaluating the system's overall performance and usability and enable identification of any issue.

2.1 Road Infrastructure Monitoring Pilot Use Case (RDP)

The objective of the Road Infrastructure Monitoring Pilot Use Case is to evaluate the effectiveness of the implemented system in accurately monitoring road traffic conditions, detecting congestion, and predicting ETA delays to enhance operational efficiency and user satisfaction.

The scope of the Road Infrastructure Monitoring Pilot includes evaluating components such as GNSS in-vehicle tracking, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) with real-time congestion and parking availability detection modules deployed on them, SENTINEL-2 satellite-based congestion detection, and various image processing and augmentation, predictive analytics, and ML algorithms. Technologies and services being assessed involve real-time traffic monitoring systems, congestion detection algorithms, ETA prediction models, and the RDP monitoring application.

The pilot will be implemented in a real-world setting focusing on major roadways and border crossings known for high traffic volumes and congestion issues. This includes deploying the system along critical transportation routes used by freight and logistics companies, particularly at the border crossing between Serbia and a neighbouring EU-member country (Horgoš-Rösztke crossing with Hungary has been initially considered at the Project proposal stage). The aim is to test the system's capabilities in an environment with significant traffic flow, diverse vehicle types, and various external factors affecting road conditions - thus the Batrovci-Bajakovo crossing with Croatia has been finally selected for the pilot evaluation as more suitable for the purpose, featuring 27% higher freight vehicles throughput, and the higher rate of goods exchange than Horgoš-Rösztke during 2023 (source: Serbian Customs Administration²).

2.1.1 Pilot-specific KPIs (RDP)

The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for the road pilot in SPATRA project are created to comprehensively evaluate the implemented solutions in terms of their effectiveness, efficiency, impact. They have been divided into categories based on the relevance to operational goals, user satisfaction, environmental sustainability and economic efficiency.

Systematic measurement of these KPIs can ensure that the SPATRA road monitoring pilot system meets its specified objectives and provides benefits for the stakeholders.

2.1.1.1 High Importance KPIs (RDP)

High importance KPIs are considered those KPIs that directly affect the efficiency of operations,

² <https://www.carina.rs/en/>

customer satisfaction and overall prototype system performance in the piloting evaluation. Included metrics assess the accuracy of key functionalities and the benefits for the environment as described in the following specification.

1. RD-KPI-1.1: Improved Accuracy on Arrival Time of Cross-Border Cargo Fleets

KPI ID	RD-HKPI-1.1
Description	Significantly improved accuracy on arrival time at final destination of cross-border cargo fleets for 90% or more of total arrivals
Relevance	- High: operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, cost management
	- Medium: regulatory compliance, competitive advantage, environmental sustainability
	- Directly impacts logistics effectiveness, resource allocation, risk reduction, business objectives
Category	Technology Specific
Target/Goal	>= 90% of total route cases
Measurement Methodology	<p>Percentage of correct ETA predictions compared to actual observed data, where a prediction within a predefined tolerance threshold Δt around the actual arrival time is considered correct (initial default Δt value is ± 15 minutes). Currently used ETA estimation is based on basic ratio of total tracked route distance divided by average vehicle moving speed, with added known duration estimations of key delaying traffic events or conditions available from online sources, like average waiting times at the cargo terminals on specific border crossings (including Batrovci) provided by the Border Police or the Auto-moto Association in Serbia (AMSS). The reliability and consistency of such estimations across the past available records cannot even be guaranteed, therefore efforts are underway in obtaining baseline values of this KPI using unified measurements with common GNSS trackers and consistent conditions. Subsequently the accuracy of the final ETA delay predictions, resulting from the fully developed RDP service features for EO and real-time monitoring and traffic conditions identification, will be evaluated on the improvement of accuracy they bring relative to the recorded baseline values.</p> <p>Δt tolerance threshold parameter can also be variable, as different ETA delays and accuracy are tolerable for different route or cargo types, affecting the sensitivity of the KPI.</p>

2. RD-KPI-1.2: Real-Time (or Near-real-time) Info on Deviations Compared to the Initial Plans

KPI ID	RD-HKPI-1.2
Description	Real-time or near-real-time deviations information compared to the initial route plans without such delay/deviation updates >85% accuracy
Relevance	- High: operational and logistics efficiency, customer satisfaction, cost minimisation - Medium: compliance, competitive advantage, environmental sustainability
Category	Technology Specific
Target/Goal	> 85%
Measurement Methodology	Percentage of real-time deviation alerts

3. RD-KPI-1.3: Carbon Emission Reduction Benefits of Reassigning Customers/Suppliers Toward Optimised Trajectories

KPI ID	RD-HKPI-1.3
Description	Emissions reduction (CO ₂ equivalent) benefits of reassigning customers or suppliers toward optimised trajectories, thereby saving fuel and reducing the harmful emission levels
Relevance	- High: environmental impact reduction, operational efficiency, cost management - Medium: stakeholder relationships, regulatory compliance, corporate responsibility - Positions businesses as leaders in sustainable logistics practices
Category	Environmental Impact
Target/Goal	Reduce by 10%
Measurement Methodology	Estimating/calculating and monitoring emissions data (on targeted NELT monitored vehicles) to quantify reductions achieved, using a custom internal formula for unspent CO ₂ emissions equivalent in ETA optimisation. Baseline inputs for the calculation are fuel type, emission standard level, vehicle type, load parameters, and tracked/telemetry data (driven distance, momentary driving regimes and patterns, average speeds, etc.) for each vehicle (some vehicle/load types are of particular interest for CO ₂ , like refrigerated cargo vehicles, having to additionally spend significant fuel even when stationary). NELT also keeps more extensive data on trucks (age, engine displacement, servicing/maintenance intervals...), so the application of an industry-standard calculation model like COPERT ³ will also be considered, as one of the goals for introduction into NELT practice.

³ <https://copert.emisia.com>

2.1.2 Target Groups for RDP

Target groups represent the subset of stakeholders identified as primary focus of activities performed during the pilot evaluation process (including data collection, user testing, feedback collection and refinement). Key target groups are described below, where they are classified as belonging to “required” or “optional” target group type. The required target groups will be included in WP4 pilot activities as they are necessary/essential for achieving defined KPI targets. The optional target groups will not be necessarily included in WP4 activities, as they are not essential for achieving defined KPIs targets. However, as they could provide additional prospective benefits for the evaluation, they are included in the RDP target groups overview in the following sections and remain prospective targets for exploitation and further uptake in continued activities beyond the Project.

2.1.2.1 RDP End-users

Logistics operations managers and dispatchers, as primary and key end-users of the road infrastructure monitoring and transport optimisation system, are expected to provide critical feedback on the system’s efficiency in improving logistics operations. They will focus on cost reduction, route optimisation, and the impact on operational planning. Their insights will help evaluate the system's effectiveness in streamlining operations and enhancing productivity. This required feedback will identify areas for improvement to better support logistics and operational efficiency.

Truck drivers as users are expected to provide some on-site information update and participative feedback. They will evaluate the RDP system and notifications/alerting usability, ease of navigation, and accuracy of ETA predictions which are crucial for scheduling and route planning. Additionally, they will optionally share real-world in-situ observations on the field situation to validate and improve monitoring accuracy and detection, and perceptions how the system affects their overall driving experience, highlighting any issues or benefits. These perceptions are, naturally, subjective, but their provision/upload to the system is intended to be supported with attachments like photos taken on-site for added evidence and reliability (or accompanying tracking data and information), and therefore are still potentially very relevant and actionable in the service workflows, even related to the monitoring and ETA delay calculation adjustments. For example, a driver waiting in a congestion line at the border can assess whether the actual real-world line length and waiting time correspond to what has been detected/estimated by the system, and report in real time if there is a notable difference - such feedback could, in turn, trigger and initiate an on-demand UAV flight to detect and confirm the actual in-situ end and moving speed of the queue, as the most accurate real-time monitoring method at disposal to the system. The drivers feedback will directly influence system improvements to meet practical needs as the piloting progresses.

Summary of this target group is provided in Table 1.

Table 1 - RDP End-Users

Type	Description	Feedback Focus	Required/Optional
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Logistics Operations Managers & Dispatchers	Primary users of the road infrastructure monitoring system, utilising it for planning and optimising freight routes.	Logistics efficiency, cost savings, operational planning.	Required
Truck Drivers	Target users mainly of mobile on-site notification and participative system features.	System usability, accuracy of ETA predictions and congestion monitoring, impact on driving experience.	Required

2.1.2.2 RDP End-user organisations

Freight and Logistics Companies managing large fleets will use the RDP prototype system for route optimisation during the pilot phase. They will provide feedback on cost savings, efficiency improvements, and overall satisfaction with the system. This required feedback will help assess the system’s impact on their operations and identify potential enhancements.

Import/Export Companies could use the system to optimise their operations and improve efficiency. They could offer feedback on operational efficiency, cost reduction, and supply chain improvements. This optional feedback would provide insights into how the system supports their logistical needs and would enable identification of areas for further optimisation.

Summary of this target group is provided in Table 2.

Table 2 – RDP End-User Organisations

Type	Description	Feedback Focus	Required/Optional
Freight and Logistics Companies	Manage large fleets and use the system for route optimisation.	Cost savings, efficiency improvements, overall satisfaction with the system.	Required
Import/Export Companies	Import/Export companies that could benefit from valuable data to optimise their operations and improve efficiency.	Operational efficiency, cost reduction, supply chain improvements.	Optional

2.1.2.3 Infrastructure managers (RDP)

Border Crossing Authorities manage operations at critical border crossings, such as the major

ones between Serbia and the neighbouring EU-member countries stated above. If using the RDP system, they could provide feedback on managing traffic congestion and improving operational efficiency. This optional feedback would be beneficial for evaluating and enhancing the system's effectiveness.

Warehouse Managers could use the monitoring data and predictions provided by the system to additionally improve and optimise the workflow of storage and distribution operations, and consequently provide feedback on the optimisation of logistics operations and efficiency improvements. This optional feedback would help identify ways to enhance the system's support for storage distribution management.

Summary of this target group is provided in Table 3 below.

Table 3 – Infrastructure Managers for RDP

Type	Description	Feedback Focus	Required/Optional
Border Crossing Authorities	Manage operations at critical border crossings.	Managing traffic congestion, improving operational efficiency.	Optional
Warehouse Managers	Manage warehouse operations and infrastructure – storage and distribution operations using data to optimise workflow.	Optimisation of logistics operations in storage distribution and management, efficiency improvements.	Optional

2.2 Railway monitoring and prediction of rail temperature zones and early warnings Pilot Use Case (RWP)

The railway monitoring and prediction of rail temperature zones and early warnings Pilot Use Case (RWP) aims to test how well the system monitors rail temperature, and predicts buckling risk to improve efficiency and safety of railway traffic. The pilot will assess Data Discovery and Processor Job Generation, Data Collection and Harmonization, Thermal Downscaling, Rail Track Temperature Prediction, Rail Track Buckling Risk Assessment, as well as main service support components such as Quality Control and Threshold Exceedance Monitoring, and WebGUI monitoring application. The pilot will be deployed on major railroads surrounding Niš (Serbia) railway juncture.

2.2.1 Pilot-specific KPIs (RWP)

The KPIs for the rail pilot in the SPATRA project are designed to thoroughly assess the solutions' effectiveness, efficiency, and impact. By the same principles as in the RDP, they are categorised by

operational goals, user satisfaction, environmental sustainability, and economic efficiency. Consistently measuring these KPIs ensures that the railway monitoring system achieves its designated goals and delivers advantages to end-users and other stakeholders.

2.2.1.1 High Importance KPIs (RWP)

High-importance KPIs are those KPIs that that impact operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, and overall system performance. These metrics evaluate the accuracy of key functions and environmental benefits.

1. RW-KPI-1.1: Prediction of rail temperatures

KPI ID	RW-HKPI-1.1
Description	At least 95% of accuracy of the rail track temperature prediction based on Copernicus data and machine learning algorithm
Relevance	- High: operational efficiency, safety, customer satisfaction, operational costs - Medium: competitive advantage, resource allocation, environmental sustainability
Category	Technology Specific
Target/Goal	> 95%
Measurement Methodology	Percentage of correctly predicted rail temperature values compared to actual observed data by in-situ sensors and UAV measurements,

2. RW-KPI-1.2: Rail buckling prediction accuracy

KPI ID	RW-HKPI-1.2
Description	At least 90% less false alerts for rail buckling risks than by current procedures based on weather forecast/air temperature
Relevance	- High: operational efficiency, safety, customer satisfaction, operational costs - Medium: competitive advantage, resource allocation, environmental sustainability
Category	Technology Specific
Target/Goal	> 90%
Measurement Methodology	Comparison of predictions for rail buckling risk by current procedures vs rail deformation data by in-situ sensors and SPATRA RWP service buckling risks prediction vs rail deformation data by in-situ sensors.

3. RW-KPI-1.3: Reduction of train speed slow orders

KPI ID	RW-HKPI-1.3
Description	At least 25% shorter duration and length of train speed slow orders that will be enabled by ordering of reducing the speed only in the hazardous rail areas predicted by the developed service.
Relevance	- High: operational efficiency, operational costs, customer satisfaction - Medium: stakeholder relationships, company public image
Category	Business Impact
Target/Goal	Reduce by 25%
Measurement Methodology	Comparison of time and network length for which slow order is issued by current procedures vs SPATRA predictions for high buckling risk expressed in network length and time

2.2.2 Target Groups for RWP

Target groups represent the subset of stakeholders identified as primary focus of activities performed during the pilot evaluation process (including data collection, user testing, feedback collection and refinement). Key target groups are described below, where they are classified as belonging to “required” or “optional” target group type. The required target groups will be included in WP4 pilot activities as they are necessary/essential for achieving defined KPI targets. The optional target groups will not be necessarily included in WP4 activities, as they are not essential for achieving defined KPIs targets. However, as they could provide additional prospective benefits for the evaluation, they are included in the RDP target groups overview in the following sections, and remain prospective targets for exploitation and further uptake in continued activities beyond the Project.

2.2.2.1. End Users for RWP

Operations dispatchers, as primary end-users, are expected to provide critical feedback on the system’s efficiency in improving prediction of buckling risk. They will concentrate on evaluation of rail pilot usability including the user interface, and prediction accuracy. This vital feedback will pinpoint areas needing pilot’s improvement to enhance operational efficiency and safety of railway transport.

Operations managers, as key end-users, are expected to provide critical feedback on the system’s efficiency in improving traffic related operations. They will focus on cost reduction and the impact on operational planning. Their insights will help evaluate the system's effectiveness in streamlining operations and enhancing efficiency and safety. This required feedback will identify areas for improvement to better support decision making regarding the buckling risk mitigation and overall effectiveness of railway traffic.

Train dispatcher, as located along the monitored routes should provide critical info about rail buckling prediction accuracy. Dispatchers play a critical role in implementing speed restrictions, known as "heat orders," as primary measure to prevent accidents related to rail buckling over potentially affected tracks. They will also be a source of information's necessary to validate high

importance KPIs as they are also a primary source of information for current procedures related to buckling prediction.

Maintenance managers will be crucial in assessing the rail pilot's performance and identifying improvements for maintenance operations. They will be focusing on usability, cost reductions, impact on maintenance planning, and worker satisfaction. The insights gained will refine and enhance the rail pilot, leading to more efficient and satisfying maintenance operations over the railway network.

Safety managers will provide comprehensive feedback on the influence of the rail pilot on the safety of railway transport. They will assess whether the pilot can enhance overall safety protocols, its potential to reduce the occurrence of accidents, and decrease emergency response times. By identifying any limitations and usage restrictions of the pilot, safety managers will highlight areas that require further attention and improvement. Their insights will be essential for ensuring that the rail pilot operates within safe parameters and contributes positively to the safety of railway network.

Summary of this target group is provided in Table 4.

Table 4 - RWP End Users

Type	Description	Feedback Focus	Required/Optional
Operations dispatcher	Primary users of the rail infrastructure monitoring system	Rail pilot usability, user interface, prediction accuracy	Required
Operations managers	Key users of the rail infrastructure monitoring system	Traffic operations efficiency, cost savings, time savings, operational planning	Required
Train dispatcher	Providing input for rail pilot validation	Prediction accuracy, time savings, gathering field info	Required
Maintenance managers	Providing info about rail pilot usability for maintenance operations	Pilot usability for maintenance operations, cost reductions, pilot impact on maintenance planning, maintenance workers satisfaction	Required
Safety manager	Assessment of rail pilot usage to traffic operations safety	Influence of pilot usage on safety of railway transport, identification of pilot limitations and usage restrictions	Required

2.2.2.2 RWP End-user organisations

Infrastructure managers (IMs) in the rail sector are the companies who are the owners and managers of the railway networks so that planned RWP solution aligns with their responsibility to optimize infrastructure performance, offering support in strategic planning and ensuring overall functionality and safety. IMs will use the RWP prototype system in the pilot phase providing feedback on the cost savings, efficiency and safety improvements, and overall satisfaction with the system. This required feedback will help to assess the system’s impact on their operations and to identify potential enhancements.

Railway Operators (ROs) are organized users of the infrastructure in the rail domain as they are the train owners that provide the service of passengers and goods transport. The utility of the planned RWP solution extends beyond infrastructure performance, providing insights into potential challenges related to environment conditions. This can contribute to informed decision-making in ROs operations and overall management of transportation resources. ROs could use the RWP system to optimise their operations and improve efficiency. They could offer feedback on operational efficiency, and cost reduction. This optional feedback would provide insights into how the system supports their logistic needs and would support identifying the areas for further system optimisation.

Summary of this target group is provided in Table 5.

Table 5 - End-user Organisations

Type	Description	Feedback Focus	Required/Optional
Railway infrastructure manager	Primarily responsible for rail infrastructure maintenance and so primary users of the rail infrastructure monitoring system	Pilot usability for traffic operations efficiency, cost savings, time savings, operational planning, safety, maintenance operations.	Required
Railway Operators	Organized users of the infrastructure in the rail domain; train owners that provide the service of passengers and goods transport	Pilot usability in supporting logistic needs, cost reduction, coping with potential challenges related to environment conditions	Optional

2.3 General Target Groups (common for both pilots, RDP and RWD)

2.3.1 Service developers

Software developers will develop and maintain the monitoring system and its components. They will provide feedback on system performance, integration issues, and potential improvements. This required feedback will be critical for ensuring the system operates effectively and efficiently.

Hardware developers will customise, adapt, integrate and deploy GNSS in-vehicle tracking devices, UAVs, and other hardware components for RDP, and the related hardware components for RWP. They will provide feedback on hardware performance, reliability, and integration with the software system. This required feedback will help ensure that the hardware components function properly and integrate seamlessly with the overall system.

System integrators will integrate various system components and ensure seamless operation. They will provide feedback on integration challenges and offer enhancement suggestions. This required feedback will be vital for ensuring that all components work together smoothly and effectively.

Summary of this target group is provided in Table 6.

Table 6 - Service Developers

Type	Description	Feedback Focus	Required/Optional
Software Developers	Develop and maintain the monitoring system and its components.	System performance, integration issues, potential improvements.	Required
Hardware Developers	Develop, customise, adapt, integrate and deploy needed hardware components for RDP and RWP.	Hardware performance, reliability, integration with software system.	Required
System Integrators	Integrate various system components and ensure seamless operation.	Integration challenges, enhancement suggestions.	Required

2.3.2 Research and Academia

Transport Analysts and Researchers could conduct studies on the effectiveness and impact of the road and rail monitoring system during the pilot phase. If doing so, they would provide scientific insights and validation of the SPATRA pilot systems' performance and benefits. This optional feedback would contribute to a deeper understanding of the systems' efficacy and potential areas for enhancement.

Summary of this target group is provided in Table 7.

Table 7 - Research and Academia

Type	Description	Feedback Focus	Required/Optional
Transport Analysts and Researchers	Conduct studies on the effectiveness and impact of the road monitoring system.	Scientific insights, validation of system performance and benefits.	Optional

2.4 General KPIs Common for Both Pilot Use Cases

2.4.1 Important General KPIs

General KPIs ensure the overall success and completeness of the pilot. They are important for evaluation of the baseline performance and pilot’s effectiveness and efficiency.

2.4.1.1 Completion Rate

KPI ID	RD-GKPI-1.1
Description	Completion Rate
Relevance	- Essential for tracking overall project progress
Category	General
Target/Goal	100%
Measurement Methodology	Percentage of successfully completed trials

2.4.1.2 Accuracy of Detection

KPI ID	RD-GKPI-1.2
Description	Accuracy of Detection/Prediction
Relevance	- High: operational efficiency, customer satisfaction
	- Essential for detecting traffic conditions and ETA predictions
	- Essential for prediction of rail temperature and estimation bucking risks
Category	Technology Specific
Target/Goal	> 90%
Measurement Methodology	Percentage of correctly identified traffic conditions and ETA predictions compared to actual observed data

2.4.1.3 User Satisfaction

KPI ID	RD-GKPI-1.3
Description	User Satisfaction
Relevance	- High: user engagement, system usability - Essential for ensuring user satisfaction and system effectiveness
Category	User Satisfaction
Target/Goal	>95% of the rating users grading the system service as Satisfactory or Highly Satisfactory on the scale
Measurement Methodology	Feedback collected through surveys and interviews, rated on a scale

2.4.1.4 Response Time

KPI ID	RD-GKPI-1.4
Description	Response Time
Relevance	- High: system performance, user satisfaction - Essential for real-time system responsiveness
Category	Performance
Target/Goal	< 20 seconds
Measurement Methodology	Average time taken for the system to process and display real-time traffic data

2.4.1.5 Data Integration Accuracy

KPI ID	RD-GKPI-1.5
Description	Data Integration Accuracy
Relevance	- High: operational efficiency, data reliability - Essential for ensuring accurate and reliable data integration
Category	Data Integration
Target/Goal	> 95%
Measurement Methodology	Consistency and correctness of data integration from various sources into the RDP/RWP system

2.4.2 Medium Importance KPIs

Medium importance KPIs evaluate user engagement, economic benefits and the system reliability. Insights are provided into the broader impact of the system on operations as well as on user satisfaction.

2.4.2.1 User Adoption Rate

KPI ID	RD-MKPI-1.1
Description	User Adoption Rate
Relevance	- High engagement - Essential for evaluating user satisfaction and system usability
Category	Usability
Target/Goal	High engagement (and consequently adoption rate)
Measurement Methodology	Number of active users (in a relevant period, daily or weekly, out of the complete number of users in a relevant role (mainly logistics operation managers/dispatchers) and relative time and frequency of use, analysed through user login data and interaction logs. Commonly used scale for subjective/perceived engaging experience, like UES-Short [1], may be additionally exploited to refine or complement these monitored/observed metrics.

2.4.2.2 Cost Savings

KPI ID	RD-MKPI-1.2
Description	Cost Savings
Relevance	- High: operational efficiency, cost management - Medium: customer satisfaction, competitive advantage
Category	Economic Impact
Target/Goal	Reduce costs by 15%
Measurement Methodology	Financial analysis comparing operational costs before and after pilot implementation

3. PILOT EVALUATION PROTOCOLS

In this Chapter, the defined procedures and mechanisms for conducting real-world demonstrations and evaluating the outcomes and results of implementation of both developed pilots i.e. developed systems, services and technologies are presented.

Pilot evaluation protocols provide a structured approach to assess these implementations systematically, capturing all relevant data to inform future developments and enhancements. The aim is to evaluate the pilot's overall performance, usability, and impact on end-users.

The **key components of the pilot evaluation protocols** are:

- Techniques for data collection
- Methods for data analysis and evaluation against defined KPIs
- Pilot schedule with deployment steps in real world setting including installation and initial testing
- Component & module tests

3.1 Data Collection Techniques

Collection of data during the pilot evaluation will involve several collection techniques:

- Surveys

Surveys will be conducted via online platforms such as SurveyMonkey or Google Forms (if needed also using paper forms). These surveys will be performed periodically, especially after major milestones or testing phases, to collect comprehensive feedback. They will collect structured feedback on various aspects of the system, including its usability, effectiveness, and impact on operations. In this way will be possible that both quantitative and qualitative data are collected to evaluate the system's performance and user satisfaction.

- System/Activity Logs

System/activity logs will involve the automatic logging of performance metrics, user interactions, and errors. This will occur continuously throughout the testing phases, focusing on capturing comprehensive data on system uptime, response times, and detection accuracy. The analysis of these logs will provide important insights into the system performance and its reliability. This will enable an evaluation of how well the system meets its operational targets.

- Direct user observations

Direct observations are required to provide important qualitative data that complements other evaluation methods. By directly observing user interactions, evaluators can gain insights into usability, ease of navigation, and user behaviour that may not be evident through surveys or system/activity logs alone. With this method can be identified specific areas for improvement with respect to user engagement with the system in real-world scenarios.

- Feedback forms

Feedback forms will be circulated at the end of workshops and testing sessions. These forms will

include structured sections for ratings and open-ended comments with the focus on collecting comprehensive feedback from users. The analysis of the feedback forms will gather scores on various system aspects and qualitative comments and suggestions. This will provide a detailed feedback for system refinement and improvement.

These techniques will provide a comprehensive and timely feedback that will direct system improvements.

3.2 Data Analysis Methods

Collected pilot data will be analysed using various techniques to enable evaluation, interpretation and understanding of system performance and user feedback and guide further improvements.

- Quantitative analysis of data will be performed to summarise them, identify any patterns or correlation using descriptive statistics, trend analysis, correlation analysis respectively.
- Qualitative analysis involves analysis of data from survey responses, interview transcripts or observation notes and performs identification and categorisation of themes and interpretation and understanding of user perspectives and behaviour.
- Comparative analysis is intended for pre-pilot and post-pilot data evaluation to compare operational efficiency, user satisfaction, impact on environment etc.
- Real-time monitoring and reporting – utilises dashboards and monitoring tools for continuous monitoring and reporting of system performance, user interactions and traffic conditions enabling immediate resolution of any emerged issue.

3.3 Evaluation Methods and Tools

Evaluation methodologies and tools that have been considered include:

1. Questionnaires (Q)

- Purpose: Collect feedback on experiences and satisfaction.
- Target Groups/Participants: End-users, service developers.
- Distribution/Format: Online surveys
- Content/Activities: Questions on usability, effectiveness, impact on operations, and suggestions for improvement.
- Output/Data Collected: Structured feedback that can be systematically analysed

2. Interviews (optional) (I)

- Purpose: Gather in-depth qualitative insights from key stakeholders.
- Target Groups/Participants: End-users, developers, other stakeholders.
- Distribution/Format: One-on-one interviews (in-person, video conferencing).

- Content/Activities: Open-ended questions on user experiences, perceived benefits, and challenges encountered.
- Output/Data Collected: Detailed qualitative understanding

3. Workshops (W)

- Purpose: Facilitate interactive sessions to demonstrate capabilities and collect feedback.
- Target Groups/Participants: End-users, developers, other stakeholders.
- Distribution/Format: Interactive sessions.
- Content/Activities: System demonstrations, hands-on sessions, group discussions.
- Output/Data Collected: Immediate feedback on system usability, functionality, and potential improvements.

4. Real-Life Testing (RLT)

- Purpose: Evaluate system performance in real-world conditions.
- Target Groups/Participants: End-users.
- Distribution/Format: Field trials (e.g., at pilot deployment sites).
- Content/Activities: RDP and RWP KPIs.
- Output/Data Collected: Real-time pilot specific data, system logs, user interaction data

3.4 Cross-relational summary of different elements in pilot evaluation process

This section summarises all the elements of the pilots’ evaluation processes and presents it in **Table 8** for the required target group types and Table 9 for the optional target group types.

Table 8 - Combined table of all segments in pilot evaluation process (required target group types)

Target Group/Type	Feedback Focus	Related KPI	Evaluation Method	Data Collection Technique	Data Analysis Method
Truck Drivers (RDP End-Users)	System usability, accuracy of ETA predictions, impact on driving experience.	User Adoption Rate, User Satisfaction	Questionnaires (Q), Real-Life Testing (RLT)	Surveys, System Logs, Direct Observation	Quantitative Analysis, Qualitative Analysis

Logistics Managers (RDP End-Users)	Logistics efficiency, cost savings, operational planning.	Cost Savings, System Uptime and Reliability	Questionnaires (Q), Interviews (I)	Surveys, Feedback Forms	Quantitative Analysis, Qualitative Analysis
Freight and Logistics Companies (RDP End-User Organisations)	Cost savings, efficiency improvements, overall satisfaction with the system.	Cost Savings, User Satisfaction	Questionnaires (Q), Real-Life Testing (RLT)	Surveys, System Logs	Quantitative Analysis, Comparative Analysis
Operations dispatcher (RWP End-Users)	Rail pilot usability, user interface, prediction accuracy	User Adoption Rate, User Satisfaction	Questionnaires (Q), Real-Life Testing (RLT)	Surveys, System Logs, Direct Observation	Quantitative Analysis, Qualitative Analysis
Operations managers (RWP End-Users)	Traffic operations efficiency, cost savings, time savings, operational planning	Cost Savings, User Satisfaction	Questionnaires (Q), Real-Life Testing (RLT)	Surveys, System Logs	Quantitative Analysis, Comparative Analysis
Train dispatcher (RWP End-Users)	Prediction accuracy, time savings, gathering field info	Accuracy of Prediction, User Satisfaction	Questionnaires (Q), Real-Life Testing (RLT)	Surveys, System Logs	Quantitative Analysis, Comparative Analysis

Maintenance managers (RWP End-Users)	Pilot usability for maintenance operations, cost reductions, pilot impact on maintenance planning, maintenance workers satisfaction	Cost Savings, User Satisfaction	Questionnaires (Q), Real-Life Testing (RLT)	Surveys, Feedback Forms	Quantitative Analysis, Qualitative Analysis
Safety manager (RWP End-Users)	Influence of pilot usage on safety of railway transport, identification of pilot limitations and usage restrictions	Accuracy of Prediction, User Satisfaction, Reliability	Questionnaires (Q), Interviews (I)	Surveys, Feedback Forms	Quantitative Analysis, Qualitative Analysis
Railway infrastructure manager (RWP End-User Organisation)	Pilot usability for traffic operations efficiency, cost savings, time savings, operational planning, safety, maintenance operations.	Cost Savings, User Satisfaction	Questionnaires (Q), Real-Life Testing (RLT)	Surveys, System Logs	Quantitative Analysis, Comparative Analysis
Software Developers (Service Developers)	System performance, integration issues, potential improvements.	System Uptime and Reliability, Response Time	Real-Time Monitoring and Reporting (RLT)	System Logs, Direct Observation, Feedback Forms	Quantitative Analysis, Real-Time Monitoring and Reporting

Hardware Developers (Service Developers)	Hardware performance, reliability, integration with software system.	System Uptime and Reliability	Real-Life Testing (RLT), Workshops (W)	System Logs, Direct Observation	Quantitative Analysis, Qualitative Analysis
System Integrators (Service Developers)	Integration challenges, enhancement suggestions.	System Uptime and Reliability	Real-Time Monitoring and Reporting (W)	System Logs, Direct Observation, Feedback Forms	Quantitative Analysis, Real-Time Monitoring and Reporting

Table 9 - Combined table of all segments in pilot evaluation process (optional target group types)

Target group/Type	Feedback Focus	Related KPI	Evaluation Method	Data Collection Technique	Data Analysis Method
Import/Export Companies (RDP End-User Organisations)	Operational efficiency, cost reduction, supply chain improvements.	Cost Savings	Questionnaires (Q), Interviews (I)	Surveys, Feedback Forms	Quantitative Analysis, Qualitative Analysis
Warehouse Managers (RDP Infrastructure Managers)	Optimisation of logistics operations, efficiency improvements.	Cost Savings	Questionnaires (Q), Interviews (I)	Surveys, Feedback Forms	Quantitative Analysis, Qualitative Analysis
Border Crossing Authorities (RDP Infrastructure Managers)	Managing/mitigating traffic congestions, improving operational efficiency.	Performance, System Uptime and Reliability	Real-Life Testing (RLT), Interviews (I)	System Logs, Direct Observation, Feedback Forms	Comparative Analysis, Real-Time Monitoring and Reporting

Railway Operators (RWP End-User Organisations)	Pilot usability in supporting logistic needs, cost reduction, coping with potential challenges related to environment conditions	Performance, Cost Savings	Questionnaires (Q), Interviews (I)	System Logs, Direct Observation, Feedback Forms	Quantitative Analysis, Qualitative Analysis
Transport Analysts and Researchers (Research and Academia)	Scientific insights, validation of system performance and benefits.	Data Integration Accuracy	Interviews (I), Comparative Analysis (W)	System Logs, Surveys, Interview Transcripts	Qualitative Analysis, Comparative Analysis

3.5 Deployment plan

Both pilot deployments follow several stages, from initial planning to final evaluation, ensuring a structured and systematic system implementation and validation. This approach enables a thorough preparation, careful monitoring and iterative improvements.

The sections below present a proposed deployment plan for the RDP and RWP including the timeline, key milestones, required resources, hardware and software required at each stage.

3.5.1 Planning and preparation

This initial stage involves finalising the deployment plan, creating the project team, and aligning key stakeholders with the project goals and timeline.

Key milestones: Deployment plan finalised and project team created

Required resources: Project management team, engaged stakeholders

Hardware required: n/a

Software required: PM software

Timeline: M1-M2

3.5.2 Prototype (modules, components) development

During this stage, initial prototypes/modules of the system components are developed to be used to test and refine the basic functionalities before full-scale deployment.

Key milestones: Initial prototypes developed and initial testing completed.

Required resources: Software and hardware developers, development tools

Hardware required: RDP - GNSS tracking devices, UAVs, test servers; RWP – meteorological stations, displacement sensors, test servers.

Software required: Development environment, simulation software.

Timeline: M3-M5

3.5.3 Lab or controlled environment testing

Prototypes (beta versions) are tested in controlled lab (or virtual/cloud in case of software) environment to identify and fix any issues. If prototypes meet the required specifications, they are ready for field deployment (pre-release version). "Lab" controlled environment can also denote an outdoor replica or model of real lifelike environment, like for example actual trucks on parking places or road in a controlled area highly similar or equivalent to real field conditions, as used for testing the UAVs and detection algorithms deployed on them (and noted explicitly as lifelike conditions in the detailed description per components following in the next section 3.6 below). In 3.6 the exact testing planned stages also elaborated for each specific component and each specific KPI related to them.

Key milestones: Perform lab tests and refine prototypes

Required resources: Test team and test users

Hardware required: RDP - GNSS tracking devices, UAVs, test servers; RWP – meteorological stations, displacement sensors, test servers.

Software required: Testing software and bug tracking software apps

Timeline: M6-M7

3.5.4 User enrolment

This stage involves recruiting and training test users who will participate in the pilots. This is required to ensure that users can effectively interact with the system and provide meaningful feedback.

Key milestones: recruitment of test users

Required resources: Training materials for users and training team

Hardware required: n/a

Software required: Training modules (with written materials, videos, quizzes, etc..)

Timeline: M8

3.5.5 Field test setup

Hardware and infrastructure necessary for both pilots are deployed in the field. This includes setting up hardware devices, network infrastructure etc.

Key milestones: Deployment of hardware in the field, setup infrastructure

Required resources: Team for field deployment and technical support

Hardware required: RDP - GNSS tracking devices, UAVs, network infrastructure; RWP – meteorological stations, displacement sensors, network infrastructure.

Software required: System integration tools (software app/system that will connect hardware and software components to work together)

Timeline: M9-M10

3.5.6 Pilot deployment

Both systems are launched during pilot deployment phase. Initial performance is monitored to ensure everything is functioning as expected. Any immediate issues are addressed.

Key milestones: Launch of pilots and monitoring of initial performance

Required resources: Project team, end-users, technical support

Hardware required: RDP - GNSS tracking devices, UAVs, network and data servers; RWP – meteorological stations, displacement sensors, network and data servers.

Software required: Monitoring software, real-time analytics tools.

Timeline: M11-M13

3.5.7 Real-world testing

The system is tested in real-world conditions to evaluate its performance. Data is collected on various parameters to validate defined KPIs

Key milestones: Conduction of real-life testing and collection of performance data

Required resources: Project team, end users, data analysts

Hardware required: GNSS tracking devices, UAVs, network and data servers.

Software required: Data collection tools, performance monitoring tools.

Timeline: M14-M16

3.5.8 Feedback collection

Feedback from users and stakeholders/target groups is collected through surveys, questionnaires, interviews, and workshops. This feedback helps in identifying areas for improvement.

Key milestones: Distribute surveys and questionnaires, perform workshops and interviews

Required resources: Survey tools, workshop organisers and interviewers

Hardware required: n/a

Software required: Survey software and software for recording interviews

Timeline: M17-M18

3.5.9 Data Analysis

Collected data is analysed and reports are generated. This stage helps the system's performance evaluation and identifies any necessary improvements.

Key milestones: Analysis of collected data and creation of reports

Required resources: Tools for statistical analysis and data analyst

Hardware required: n/a

Software required: Excel, R, SPSS and data visualisation tools

Timeline: M19-M20

3.5.10 Corrective actions

Based on the performed analysis, improvements are implemented, and the system is tested again to ensure that the issues are resolved. This stage ensures the system meets the required standards before the final evaluation.

Key milestones: performing improvements and repeating tests

Required resources: Development and testing team

Hardware required: GNSS tracking devices, UAVs, network and data servers.

Software required: Development environment, testing tools.

Timeline: M21-M22

3.5.11 Final evaluation

A thorough assessment of the system is conducted, and a final report is prepared. This stage merges all findings and ensures the system is ready for full-scale deployment.

Key milestones: Conduction of full assessment and preparation of the final report

Required resources: Project team and stakeholders

Hardware required: n/a

Software required: Reporting software/apps (Power Point and MS Word)

Timeline: M23-M24

3.6 Description of tests per component (RDP)

To test each component effectively, the testing process should align with the stages in deployment plan. Components of a system (as described in D2.1) that need to go through testing phases are:

- GNSS In-Vehicle Tracking
- Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)
- SENTINEL-2 Truck Detection
- SENTINEL-2 Multispectral Temporal Offset-Based Method
- Additional and Alternative Supporting Detection Methods from EO Sources
- EGNSS Truck Localisation and Telemetry Tracking
- Parking Drone Detection Algorithm
- Drone-Based Congestion Detection Algorithm
- Extended Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) Calculation
- RDP Monitoring Application

Figure 1 below provides again for reference the overview of the high-level architecture and system organisation supporting the RDP service, as already presented in the Deliverable D2.1, illustrating the positioning and relations of the individual components in the system structure. More detailed description of it can be found in D2.1, Section 3.1.1. Each of the main listed components will go through the specified test phases, as described in the following section.

Figure 1. High-level RDP-supporting system architecture and organization, reference from D2.1

3.6.1 GNSS In-Vehicle Tracking

Evaluation goals for this component is to ensure the GNSS in-vehicle tracking system operates correctly, accurately, reliably, and integrates seamlessly with the overall system.

EGNSS In-Vehicle Tracking: Focuses on technical specifications/aspects like positioning accuracy, signal stability, device operational performance, telemetry data accuracy, integration, and user satisfaction.

3.6.1.1 Objectives are:

- Validate the positioning accuracy and signal stability of the GNSS devices.
- Assess operational performance, including battery life and memory usage.
- Ensure accurate and reliable telemetry data.
- Test integration and compatibility with other system components.
- Gather user feedback to identify areas for improvement.

3.6.1.2 KPIs for GNSS In-Vehicle Tracking

Accuracy of GNSS Positioning (RD-KPI-2.1)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve positioning accuracy of less than 2.5 meters Circular Error Probable (CEP) at -130dBm.
- **Measurement Methodology:** The accuracy will be measured by comparing the GNSS data with known routes and checkpoints.
- **Method:** This involves conducting a Signal Accuracy Test, where GNSS devices are installed in vehicles and their movements are tracked over predefined routes.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be evaluated during Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

Stability of GNSS Signal (RD-KPI-2.2)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure minimal signal dropouts and quick recovery times.
- **Measurement Methodology:** The stability of the GNSS signal will be recorded, focusing on signal dropouts, latency, and recovery times.
- **Method:** The Signal Stability Test will monitor GNSS signals in various environments, including urban, rural, and tunnels.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be assessed during Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

GNSS Device Operational Performance (RD-KPI-2.3)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve 9 hours of continuous operation and up to 20 days in low-power mode.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Monitor the device's battery life, memory usage, and performance in different temperature ranges.
- **Method:** This will be conducted through device testing.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Evaluated during Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

Accuracy and Reliability of Telemetry Data (RD-KPI-2.4)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure telemetry data accuracy exceeds 95%.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Validate telemetry data against known parameters.
- **Method:** The Telemetry Data Test involves collecting telemetry data, such as speed and engine status, during tracking.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be assessed during Field Setup, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

Integration and Compatibility (RD-KPI-2.5)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve 100% compatibility and data integration accuracy.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Test the data flow and compatibility with existing systems.
- **Method:** The Integration Test will evaluate the data flow and compatibility.

- **Assessment Stage(s):** Assessed during Field Setup, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

User Satisfaction (RD-KPI-2.6)

- **Target/Goal:** Attain high satisfaction ratings from end-users.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Collect feedback through surveys and interviews, then analyse user satisfaction scores and comments.
- **Method:** User satisfaction will be evaluated by collecting feedback through surveys and interviews.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be assessed during Feedback Collection and Final Evaluation stages.

3.6.2 Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)

The evaluation goal for the UAV component is to ensure that the system operates correctly, provides high-quality data, maintains stable connectivity processes and efficient execution of on-board running algorithms and logic, integrates well with other systems and meets end-user requirements.

Objectives:

- **Validate flight stability:** Ensure UAVs can maintain stable flight under various weather conditions and altitudes.
- **Assess image capture quality:** Evaluate the quality, accuracy, and coverage area of images captured by the UAVs for traffic monitoring.
- **Ensure signal and connectivity stability:** Monitor the stability and reliability of signal and data transmission rates.
- **Evaluate on-board processing performance:** Assess the efficiency and accuracy of on-board data processing capabilities.
- **Test integration with parking detection algorithm:** Ensure accurate and seamless integration for detecting available parking spaces.

Gather user feedback: Collect and analyse user satisfaction to identify areas for improvement.

3.6.2.1 KPIs for Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

Image Capture Quality (RD-KPI-3.1)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve high-quality image capture for traffic monitoring.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Analyse image quality, resolution, and coverage area.
- **Method:** The Image Capture Test involves using UAVs to capture images of road traffic at different viewing angles.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be assessed during Prototype Development, Lab and Lifelike Conditions Testing, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

Signal and Connectivity Stability (RD-KPI-3.2)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure stable signal and connectivity for real-time data transmission.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Monitor signal stability and data transmission rates.
- **Method:** This will be conducted through signal stability and connectivity tests (with the underlying supporting APIs and the orchestrating gateway for data collection/exchange and UAVs routing management, as shown on the system architecture and organisation diagrams in D2.1).
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Evaluated during Lab and Lifelike Conditions Testing, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

On-Board Processing Performance (RD-KPI-3.3)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve efficient on-board data processing for real-time analysis.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Assess processing speed and accuracy of on-board hardware.
- **Method:** The On-Board Processing Test involves evaluating the UAV's on-board processing capabilities.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be assessed during Prototype Development, Lab and Lifelike Conditions Testing, and Real-Life Testing stages.

Integration with the Parking Detection Algorithm (RD-KPI-3.4)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure seamless integration and accurate parking detection.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Compare detected parking spaces with actual availability.
- **Method:** The Integration Test which involves deploying drones to monitor parking areas and detecting available spaces.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be evaluated during Field Setup, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

User Satisfaction (RD-KPI-3.5)

- **Target/Goal:** Attain high satisfaction ratings from end-users.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Collect feedback through surveys and interviews, then analyse user satisfaction scores and comments.
- **Method:** User satisfaction will be evaluated by collecting feedback through surveys and interviews.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be assessed during Feedback Collection and Final Evaluation stages.

3.6.3 SENTINEL-2 Congestion Detection

The primary goal of evaluating the SENTINEL-2 Truck Detection component is to ensure that the system can effectively detect and monitor freight vehicles in traffic congestions using high-resolution satellite images. This involves validating the accuracy and reliability of congestion detection, assessing the temporal resolution, and integrating additional data sources to enhance detection capabilities.

Objectives:

- **Validate congestion detection accuracy:** Ensure that the system accurately detects trucks in high-resolution satellite images.
- **Assess temporal resolution:** Evaluate the system's ability to consistently detect truck congestions at different times.
- **Enhance image preprocessing:** Improve the preprocessing steps, including image segmentation and multiplication, to support accurate truck detection.
- **Integrate additional data sources:** Correlate satellite image data with data from other sources to enhance detection accuracy and reliability.
- **Evaluate user satisfaction:** Gather feedback from end-users to identify areas for improvement and ensure the system meets practical needs.

3.6.3.1 KPIs for SENTINEL-2 Truck Lines and Congestions Detection

Truck Detection Accuracy (RD-KPI-3.1)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve > 90% accuracy in detecting truck lines and congestions.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Compare detected truck lines against ground truth data.
- **Method:** Image Analysis Test: Process SENTINEL-2 satellite images to detect truck lines.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Evaluated during Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

Temporal Detection Consistency (RD-KPI-3.2)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure high consistency in detection over time.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Evaluate detection consistency over different times.
- **Method:** Temporal Resolution Test: Analyse the ability to detect trucks at different times.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Evaluated during Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

Image Preprocessing Enhancement Effectiveness (RD-KPI-3.3)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve high effectiveness in image preprocessing enhancements.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Assess performance of preprocessing steps.
- **Method:** Image Segmentation Test: Improve segmentation, multiplication, and enhancement methods.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Evaluated during Prototype Development, Lab Testing, and Pilot Deployment stages.

Data Integration Accuracy (RD-KPI-3.4)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure > 95% accuracy in data integration.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Validate the integration of satellite data with other sources.
- **Method:** Data Correlation Test: Correlate satellite image data with data from additional

sources.

- **Assessment Stage(s):** Evaluated during Field Setup, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

User Satisfaction (RD-KPI-3.5)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve high satisfaction ratings from end-users.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Collect feedback through surveys and interviews, analyse satisfaction scores and comments.
- **Method:** User Satisfaction: Collect feedback through surveys and interviews.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Evaluated during Feedback Collection and Final Evaluation stages.

3.6.4 Additional and Alternative Supporting Detection Methods from EO Sources

The goals here are:

- To enhance the spatial resolution of SENTINEL-2 images using super-resolution and other techniques for improved detection accuracy of parking places and truck congestions, specified in D2.1 section 3.1.2.2.2.
- To ensure the integration of enhanced images from other EO data sources and gather user feedback for usability and effectiveness improvements.

Objectives:

- Improve the spatial resolution and accuracy of SENTINEL-2 images using alternative supporting image enhancement techniques, detection methods, and additional EO sources.
- Achieve high accuracy in detecting parking place availability and occupancy through enhanced images.
- Validate the performance of resolution-improving models trained on Google Earth data.
- Ensure accurate data integration and correlation between enhanced images and other EO data sources.
- Collect and analyse user feedback to refine and enhance the detection methods.

3.6.4.1 KPIs for Additional and Alternative Supporting Detection Methods from EO Sources

Super-Resolution Image Enhancement (RD-KPI-4.1)

- **Target/Goal:** Improve spatial resolution of SENTINEL-2 images from native 10m per pixel to 5m or better.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Evaluate the enhanced image quality and resolution.
- **Method:** Super-Resolution Test: Use deep learning models to enhance SENTINEL-2 images.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Evaluated during Prototype Development, Lab Testing, and Pilot Deployment stages.

Accuracy of Enhanced Detection (RD-KPI-4.2)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve > 90% accuracy in detecting parking place availability and occupancy.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Compare detected parking availability against ground truth data.
- **Method:** Image Analysis Test: Process enhanced satellite images to detect parking places.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Evaluated during Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

Model Training Effectiveness (RD-KPI-4.3)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure effective training of resolution-improving models.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Validate model performance using Google Earth data as ground truth.
- **Method:** Model Training Test: Train and validate the deep learning models.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Evaluated during Prototype Development and Lab Testing stages.

Data Integration Accuracy (RD-KPI-4.4)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure > 95% accuracy in integrating enhanced image data with other sources.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Validate the integration and correlation of enhanced images with other EO data sources.
- **Method:** Data Correlation Test: Integrate and correlate enhanced image data with additional sources.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Evaluated during Field Setup, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

User Satisfaction (RD-KPI-4.5)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve high satisfaction ratings from end-users regarding the enhanced image quality and detection accuracy.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Collect feedback through surveys and interviews, analyse satisfaction scores and comments.
- **Method:** User Satisfaction: Collect feedback through surveys and interviews.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Evaluated during Feedback Collection and Final Evaluation stages.

Detection Reliability Over Time (RD-KPI-4.6)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure high reliability of detection over different time intervals.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Analyse detection consistency using enhanced images at different times.
- **Method:** Temporal Consistency Test: Evaluate detection reliability using temporally enhanced images.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Evaluated during Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

3.6.5 EGNSS Truck Localisation and Telemetry Tracking

EGNSS Truck Localization and Telemetry Tracking focuses on the practical application of GNSS data for real-time traffic monitoring, congestion detection, ETA prediction, and user satisfaction with real-time information.

Goals

- Improve the accuracy of vehicle tracking and fleet management using EGNSS and Copernicus services.
- Enable deeper trend analysis of time-series data, extending into the past before SPATRA.

Objectives

- Provide key inputs for predicting congestion and ETA delays in logistics network flows.
- Ensure seamless integration and data transmission from GNSS trackers to the RDP Core cloud.

3.6.5.1 KPIs for EGNSS Truck Localization and Telemetry Tracking

Accuracy of Vehicle Tracking (RD-KPI-5.1)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve a positioning accuracy of < 2.5m CEP.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Compare GNSS data with known routes and checkpoints, and UAV-sourced positioning detection.
- **Method:** Install GNSS devices in vehicles and track movements over predefined routes.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real - Life Testing.

Stability of GNSS Signal (RD-KPI-5.2)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure minimal signal dropouts and quick recovery.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Record signal dropouts, latency, and recovery times.
- **Method:** Monitor GNSS signal in various environments (urban, rural, tunnels).
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

Operational Performance of GNSS Device (RD-KPI-5.3)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure 9 hours of continuous operation and up to 20 days in low-power mode.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Monitor battery life, memory usage, and performance in different temperature ranges.
- **Method:** Device testing in various conditions.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

Accuracy and Reliability of Telemetry Data (RD-KPI-5.4)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve > 95% accuracy in telemetry data.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Validate telemetry data against known parameters.
- **Method:** Collect telemetry data (e.g., speed, engine status) during tracking.

- **Assessment Stage(s):** Field Setup, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

Integration and Compatibility (RD-KPI-5.5)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure 100% compatibility and data integration accuracy.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Test data flow and compatibility with existing systems.
- **Method:** Integration Test: Test data flow and compatibility with existing systems.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Field Setup, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

User Satisfaction (RD-KPI-5.6)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve high satisfaction ratings from end-users.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Collect feedback through surveys and interviews, analyze user satisfaction scores and comments.
- **Method: User Satisfaction:** Collect feedback through surveys and interviews.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Feedback Collection, Final Evaluation

3.6.6 In-situ Parking Detection Algorithm

Goals:

- Ensure the accuracy and reliability of the drone-based truck parking detection system in various environmental conditions and operational scenarios.
- Validate the effectiveness of the OS-NMA authentication in preventing spoofing and ensuring secure navigation data.

Objectives:

- Validate the drone's ability to accurately detect and classify trucks in various parking scenarios and assess the precision of parking space occupancy detection.
- Ensure continuous OS-NMA verification to maintain data integrity and prevent spoofing, and evaluate the system's operational performance, including data processing, communication, and reporting.
- Collect and analyze user feedback on the system's usability and real-time information accuracy.

3.6.6.1 KPIs for In-situ Parking Occupancy Detection Algorithm

Detection Accuracy (RD-KPI-6.1)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve > 95% accuracy in detecting and classifying trucks.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Compare detected trucks against ground truth data.
- **Method:** Image and LIDAR data processing using detection algorithms like YOLO and SSD.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab and Lifelike Conditions Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

Parking Space Occupancy Detection (RD-KPI-6.2)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve > 90% accuracy in determining parking space occupancy.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Compare detected occupancy status with actual parking space usage.
- **Method:** Image processing and pattern recognition for parking space analysis.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab and Lifelike Conditions Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

OS-NMA Verification (RD-KPI-6.3)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure 100% successful verification of GNSS data integrity.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Monitor OS-NMA authentication processes and detect any anomalies.
- **Method:** Continuous OS-NMA verification during drone operations.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab and Lifelike Conditions Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

Operational Performance (RD-KPI-6.4)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure smooth operation with minimal downtime (under 20 seconds response time for on-demand in-situ detection) and high data processing efficiency.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Monitor system performance metrics such as uptime, processing speed, and data transmission reliability.
- **Method:** Performance monitoring during all operational stages.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab and Lifelike Conditions Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

User Satisfaction (RD-KPI-6.5)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve high satisfaction ratings from end-users (truck drivers and parking managers).
- **Measurement Methodology:** Collect feedback through surveys and interviews, analyze user satisfaction scores and comments.
- **Method:** User feedback collection and analysis.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Feedback Collection, Final Evaluation

Data Integrity and Security (RD-KPI-6.6)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure data integrity and security throughout the operation.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Monitor and verify data security protocols and integrity checks.
- **Method:** Continuous security assessments and OS-NMA authentication monitoring.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab and Lifelike Conditions Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

3.6.7 Drone-Based In-situ Congestion Detection Algorithm

Evaluation Goals

- To ensure the accuracy and reliability of the drone-based truck congestion detection system.
- To validate the effectiveness of advanced object detection techniques, including YOLO and GGT-YOLO, in monitoring truck congestion near borders.

Objectives

- Validate the drone's ability to accurately detect and classify trucks in various congestion scenarios, ensuring precise distance measurements using LIDAR or ultrasonic sensors.
- Assess the precision of congestion metrics, including truck density and average distance from the border, under various environmental conditions and operational scenarios.
- Collect and analyze user feedback on the system's usability and real-time congestion information accuracy.

3.6.7.1 KPIs for Drone-Based In-situ Congestion Detection Algorithm

Detection Accuracy (RD-KPI-7.1)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve > 95% accuracy in detecting and classifying truck congestions.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Compare detected trucks against ground truth data.
- **Method:** Utilize image and sensor data processing techniques such as YOLO and GGT-YOLO to analyze the data.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be evaluated during the Prototype Development, Lab and Lifelike Conditions Testing, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

Distance Measurement Precision (RD-KPI-7.2)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve high precision in distance measurements.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Compare the measured distances with actual distances.
- **Method:** Use LIDAR or ultrasonic sensors for accurate distance measurement.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be assessed during Prototype Development, Lab and Lifelike Conditions Testing, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

Congestion Metrics Accuracy (RD-KPI-7.3)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve > 90% accuracy in calculating congestion metrics.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Compare calculated congestion metrics with actual traffic conditions.
- **Method:** Analyze truck density and average distance from the border.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be evaluated during Prototype Development, Lab and Lifelike Conditions Testing, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

Operational Performance (RD-KPI-7.4)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure smooth operation with minimal downtime and high data processing

efficiency.

- **Measurement Methodology:** Monitor system performance metrics such as uptime, processing speed, and data transmission reliability.
- **Method:** Performance monitoring during all operational stages.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be assessed during Lab and Lifelike Conditions Testing, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

User Satisfaction (RD-KPI-7.5)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve high satisfaction ratings from end-users (truck drivers and border control managers).
- **Measurement Methodology:** Collect feedback through surveys and interviews, and analyze user satisfaction scores and comments.
- **Method:** User feedback collection and analysis.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be evaluated during the Feedback Collection and Final Evaluation stages.

Data Integrity and Security (RD-KPI-7.6)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure data integrity and security throughout the operation.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Monitor and verify data security protocols and integrity checks.
- **Method:** Continuous security assessments and OS-NMA authentication monitoring.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be assessed during Prototype (beta and pre-beta versions) Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

3.6.8 Extended Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) Calculation Goals

The primary goals of evaluating the extended ETA calculation component are to ensure the system's accuracy, reliability, and adaptability in providing precise ETAs for trucks. This includes incorporating dynamic factors such as border congestions, weather conditions, and extraordinary events. Additionally, the goal is to enhance the system's predictive capabilities and improve the overall efficiency of logistics operations.

Objectives

- **Validate Accuracy:** Ensure the accuracy of the ETA calculations by comparing predicted ETAs with actual arrival times under various conditions.
- **Assess Influence of Dynamic Factors:** Evaluate how different dynamic factors (e.g., weather, border events, seasonal patterns) impact the overall ETA and quantify their relative importance.
- **Enhance Predictive Capabilities:** Improve the predictive algorithms using ensemble methods and meta-learning to adaptively assign importance scores to various factors.
- **Gather User Feedback:** Collect feedback from end-users to understand the usability and effectiveness of the extended ETA calculations and make necessary improvements based on this feedback.

3.6.8.1 KPIs for Extended Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) Calculation

ETA Prediction Accuracy (RD-KPI-8.1)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve a deviation of less than 5% from actual arrival times.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Compare predicted ETAs with actual arrival times.
- **Method:** Utilize ensemble algorithms to enhance prediction accuracy by considering various dynamic factors.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

Impact of Dynamic Factors (RD-KPI-8.2)

- **Target/Goal:** Quantify the influence of dynamic factors on ETA with high accuracy.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Use sensitivity analysis and meta-learning techniques to evaluate the impact of individual factors.
- **Method:** Employ classifiers like AdaBoost, Naïve Bayes, SVM, and random forests to assign importance scores.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

User Satisfaction (RD-KPI-8.3)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve high satisfaction ratings from end-users regarding the accuracy and reliability of ETA predictions.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Collect feedback through surveys and interviews, analyze user satisfaction scores and comments.
- **Method:** User feedback collection and analysis.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Feedback Collection, Final Evaluation.

System Adaptability (RD-KPI-8.4)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure the system can adapt to changing conditions and new data sources.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Monitor system performance and adaptability metrics.
- **Method:** Evaluate system performance under different scenarios and adjust algorithms as needed.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

Reliability of Integrated Data Sources (RD-KPI-8.5)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure seamless integration and reliability of various data sources (e.g., EGNSS data, satellite images, weather data).
- **Measurement Methodology:** Test data integration and reliability across different sources.
- **Method:** Continuous monitoring and verification of data integration processes.

- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing

3.6.9 RDP Monitoring Application

Goals:

- Ensure the functionality, usability, and performance of the RDP Monitoring Application in providing accurate traffic flow monitoring and logistics predictions.
- Evaluate user satisfaction and the effectiveness of the alerting and notification features.

Objectives:

- Validate the application's ability to accurately monitor traffic flows and predict logistics.
- Assess the usability and user satisfaction of the web-based graphical interface.
- Evaluate the effectiveness of the alerting and notification features in providing timely and actionable information to end users.

3.6.9.1 KPIs for RDP Monitoring Application

Functionality Accuracy (RD-KPI-9.1)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve > 95% accuracy in processing and responding to user requests.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Compare the application's responses to user requests with expected outcomes.
- **Method:** Functional testing of various user requests and responses.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

User Interface Usability (RD-KPI-9.2)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve high usability ratings from end-users.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Collect user feedback on UI ease of use, navigation, and overall experience through surveys and usability testing.
- **Method:** Usability testing sessions and user surveys.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

Data Integration Accuracy (RD-KPI-9.3)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure 100% data integration accuracy between front-end and back-end services.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Test data flow and consistency between UI and back-end data sources.
- **Method:** Integration testing and data consistency checks.

- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing

Performance Under Load (RD-KPI-9.4)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure stable performance with response times < 20 seconds under various load conditions (including advanced recognition or predictive algorithms execution).
- **Measurement Methodology:** Monitor application performance metrics such as response times, stability, and error rates.
- **Method:** Performance testing under different simulated load conditions.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

User Satisfaction with Alerts (RD-KPI-9.5)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve high satisfaction ratings from end-users regarding the alerting and notification features.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Collect feedback on the usefulness and timeliness of alerts through surveys and interviews.
- **Method:** User feedback collection and analysis.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Feedback Collection, Final Evaluation

User Satisfaction with Alerts (RD-KPI-9.5)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve high satisfaction ratings from end-users regarding the alerting and notification features.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Collect feedback on the usefulness and timeliness of alerts through surveys and interviews.
- **Method:** User feedback collection and analysis.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Feedback Collection, Final Evaluation

3.6.10 RDP Pilot deployment

The pilot deployment phase will involve the implementation of the road infrastructure monitoring system in the relevant operational environment and real-world settings. This phase will focus on evaluating and validating the system's performance, gathering user feedback and identifying areas for improvement.

The execution of the pilot will include deploying and testing the integrated modules in the logistics and transportation operations premises of the NELT company, and on-site in the vicinity area of a selected border crossing - Batrovci-Bajakovo between Serbia and Croatia, recently extended in capacity (and exceeding significantly the initially planned Horgoš-Röske with Hungary, as mentioned in section 2.1).

The pilot will be conducted in a controlled manner - with the close involvement of the technical team who will be performing surveillance and supervision of the user interactions with the system, audit logs and system activities tracing data (additionally to the unit and integration tests outputs). Data on the performance of the integrated modules will be collected and analysed, enabling evaluation of the effectiveness and efficiency of each module.

Figure 2. Batrovci-Bajakovo border crossing between Serbia and Croatia after the recent 2018 extension, nominally enabling up to 50% increased throughput capacity (image: CIP Institute of Transportation⁴)

Figure 3. Satellite map view of the Batrovci (east/right) - Bajakovo (west/left) crossing

⁴ <https://sicip.rs/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/01-10-scaled.jpg>

Figure 4. A congestion on the Batrovci-Bajakovo crossing (image:AMSS-Serbian National Automobile Club live web camera⁵)

The deployment will be executed in several stages with each stage assigned specific internal milestones, resources, and required tools, aligning with the activities outlined in Tasks 4.1 to 4.4 of WP4.

First stage will focus on the establishment and configuration of data collection, and in-situ monitoring and tracking infrastructure deployment. It is practically already underway, with the in-vehicle EGNSS-supporting trackers (Astra Telematics AT242, as specified in D2.1 section 3.1.2.1.1) currently being in delivery and awaited to be installed in the NELT trucks. In parallel, the UAVs equipped for in-situ congestions and parking occupancy detection are to be tested, and training image datasets acquired on generic trucks and traffic/parking settings as well as on the actual pilot location close to the border crossing, if not requiring excessive administrative burden using locally available UAVs. The detection algorithms trained on the referent datasets generated or acquired from on-site, historical and online sources, and the data acquisition and pre-processing/augmentation API packages and modules deployed and tested as they are implemented.

Integration testing and mostly technical validation of different modules interacting and orchestrated together will follow, including the most advanced processing, predictive, and delay estimation analytics, planned to be reaching completion on the development side in the meantime. Deployment and evaluation of deployed UI components and controls is planned in parallel as they get released, with increasing involvement of the end users in the NELT headquarters distributive-operational logistics centre and in the field and trucks, and closely followed and continuously qualitatively and subjectively assessed outputs and performance of the complete service system, using historically collected, generated test-case, and real-life data inputs.

⁵ <https://kamere.amss.org.rs/batrovci1/batrovci1.m3u8>

Figure 5. Wider zoomed-out enhanced view of the highway approach to the Batrovci crossing, with the detectable line of waiting trucks marked yellow on the left side, and a monitored parking area of interest on the right side

Finally, the systematization and thorough analysis of the gathered performance tracking and evaluation feedback data against the predefined KPIs is to identify deviations or gaps, and point to solutions for final refinements or improvements in T4.4, as well as insights into the effectiveness and potential impact on the NELT operations streamlining and optimisation in exploitation of the RDP services by the end and beyond the Project.

3.7 Description of tests per component (RWP)

Figure 6. High-level architecture of SPATRA RWP service

Figure 6 above provides an overview of the high-level architecture of the RWP service. A more detailed description of the individual components can be found in Deliverable D2.1, Section 3.2.1, RWP service architecture. The tests of the main components are described in the following section.

3.7.1 Data Discovery and Processor Job Generation

The Data Discovery and Processor Job Generation (DDPJG) component is responsible for monitoring data sources for newly published data, generating RTBR subtasks and tile-subtasks from RTBR tasks, and creating STAC collection and item templates for RTBR tile-subtasks. It ensures timely discovery of new data and efficient organization of processing tasks. The primary goals of the DDPJG are to maintain up-to-date information from various sources and optimize data processing through intelligent task management.

Objectives:

- Monitor all data sources continuously and detect new data publications within specified timeframes.
- Generate and manage RTBR tasks, subtasks, and tile-subtasks with appropriate linking.
- Create STAC collections and item templates for processed data.
- Optimize tiling sizes for different data products to meet timeliness requirements.

3.7.1.1 KPIs for Data Discovery and Processor Job Generation

Time Behaviour – Timeliness of Data Discovery (RW-KPI-1.1)

- **Target/Goal:** Detect new data publications within 5 minutes of their release.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Track the time difference between data publication and detection timestamps.
- **Method:** Unit testing
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing

Time Behaviour – New Data Timeliness (RW-KPI-1.2)

- **Target/Goal:** All new data is detected within the 4-hour window from its publication time.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Track the time difference between data publication and detection timestamps.
- **Method:** Unit testing
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing

3.7.2 Data Collection and Harmonization

The Data Collection and Harmonization (DCH) component is responsible for continuously performing data discovery, collection, preprocessing, and harmonization for the required data products. It ensures that data are ready for further processing through operations such as mosaicking, cloud masking, clipping, reprojecting, and calculating indices like Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI). The primary goals of the DCH are to maintain an up-to-date and standardized dataset from various sources, optimize data processing efficiency, and provide high-quality, harmonized data for subsequent analysis.

Objectives:

- Continuously collect and harmonize all required data products.
- Access and download targeted data from various data sources.
- Implement efficient data processing techniques, including chunked downloads and moving window approaches.
- Apply necessary preprocessing steps such as clipping, reprojecting, and mosaicking.
- Ensure quick integration of new data sources and products.

- Develop robust retry policies for handling data unavailability.

3.7.2.1 KPIs for Data Collection and Harmonization

Data Collection Completeness (RW-KPI-2.1)

- **Target/Goal:** Successfully collect and harmonize required data products from all specified sources.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Verification against predefined data product list that all required data products can be collected and correctly harmonized.
- **Method:** Unit testing of data collection and harmonization of each data product.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing

3.7.3 Thermal Downscaling

The Thermal Downscaling component is responsible for improving the spatial resolution of the Land Surface Temperature (LST) data from Sentinel-3, MODIS and MSG (provided by CLMS). Based on machine learning approaches, this component will downscale LST data from resolution such as 1km and 5km to the required resolution of 500m or finer. The primary goal of the Thermal Downscaling component is to increase the spatial resolution of LST data, making it more suitable for localised monitoring and analysis of the railway environment.

Objectives

- Implement near real-time downscaling methods suitable for operational use.
- Achieve a target resolution of 500m or finer for all input LST data.
- Maintain high accuracy in downscaled temperatures, staying within 3°C of actual temperatures.
- Complete the downscaling process within specified time constraints.

3.7.3.1 KPIs for Thermal Downscaling

Downscaling Accuracy (RW-KPI-3.1)

- **Target/Goal:** Implementation of a downscaling algorithm that improves the spatial resolution to 500m or finer and ensures that the downscaled temperatures are within ± 3 °C of the actual temperatures in 95 % of cases.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Compare downscaled values with values from high-resolution reference LST imagery, such as Landsat 8/9 LST imagery, and calculate statistical metrics such as Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Coefficient of Determination (R^2). In addition, use an 80:20 split of training and test data.
- **Method:** Functional testing and comprehensive statistical evaluation and validation.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing, Data Analysis.

Time Behaviour (RW-KPI-3.2)

- **Target/Goal:** Complete downscaling process in less than 30 minutes.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Measure the time taken from input to output for the downscaling process.
- **Method:** Performance testing for all data products.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing,

Model Generalization (RW-KPI-3.3)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure consistent performance across various environments and track locations.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Test the model on diverse datasets representing different geographical regions, seasons, and land cover types. Calculate and compare statistical metrics such as RMSE, MAE and R^2 for each scenario using high-resolution data as a reference. In addition, use an 80:20 split of training and test data.
- **Method:** Model validation using Cross-Validation testing and Out-of-Sample testing.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing, Data Analysis.

3.7.4 Rail Track Temperature Prediction

The Rail Track Temperature Prediction (RTTP) component is designed to forecast rail track temperatures (RTT) at a high spatial resolution of 500m or finer for a 24-hour window. It aims to provide accurate, timely predictions to support proactive maintenance and enhance operational safety in railway systems. The primary goals of the RTTP component are to implement machine learning approaches for near real-time predictions, ensure hourly forecasts over a 24-hour period, and maintain high accuracy within specified time constraints. Additionally, a crucial goal is to capture and predict local temperature variations at a high spatial resolution of 500m or finer. This focus on local-scale prediction enables the RTTP to account for local effects and provide detailed temperature forecasts for specific sections of rail tracks, enhancing the precision and relevance of the predictions for railway operations and safety management.

Objectives:

- Implement machine learning models suitable for near real-time RTT prediction.
- Provide hourly RTT predictions for a 24-hour forecast window.
- Complete predictions within 10 minutes to support timely decision-making.
- Ensure predicted temperatures do not deviate from actual temperatures by more than 5°C.
- Utilize downscaled LST data at 500m resolution or finer as input for the prediction model.

3.7.4.1 KPIs for Rail Track Temperature Prediction

Prediction Accuracy (RW-KPI-4.1)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve RTT predictions within $\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ of actual temperatures.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Compare predicted RTT values with actual measured temperatures collected from RTT sensors or drone using statistical metrics such as MAE and RMSE.
- **Method:** Statistical analysis
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing, Data Analysis.

Time Behaviour (RW-KPI-4.2)

- **Target/Goal:** Complete RTT prediction in less than 10 minutes.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Measure the time taken from input to output for the RTT prediction process.
- **Method:** Performance testing
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing

Model Generalization (RW-KPI-4.3)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure consistent performance across various weather conditions and track locations.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Test the model on diverse datasets representing different weather conditions and geographical locations. Calculate performance metrics for each scenario and compare them.
- **Method:** Model validation using Cross-Validation testing and Out-of-Sample testing.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing, Data Analysis

3.7.5 Rail Track Buckling Risk Assessment (UNI)

The primary goals of evaluating the rail track buckling risk assessment component are to ensure that the system can accurately assess the rail track buckling risk using the predicted rail track temperature. Remaining goals are to evaluate the efficiency of the component, which is reflected in shortening the duration and length of train speed slow orders, and user satisfaction.

Objectives are:

- Validate the accuracy of the rail track buckling risk assessment.
- Evaluate the efficiency of the rail track buckling risk assessment.
- Gather user feedback to identify areas for improvement.

3.7.5.1 KPIs for Rail Track Buckling Risk Assessment

Accuracy of the Rail Track Buckling Risk Assessment (RW-KPI-5.1)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve at least 25% fewer false alerts for rail buckling risks than by current procedures based on weather forecast / air temperature.
- **Measurement Methodology:** The accuracy will be measured by comparing rail track buckling risk assessed using the rail track buckling risk assessor, and current procedures based on weather forecast / air temperature, for a certain period of time, considering in situ rail track temperature measurements, and optionally in situ rail lateral displacement measurements.
- **Method:** Predicted rail track temperature data will be used for rail track buckling risk assessments, considering critical rail temperatures available for different countries and rail curvatures. In addition, algorithm for rail track buckling risk assessment can incorporate site-specific risk factors, which are track and traffic specific, for more accurate assessment.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be assessed during Prototype Development, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

Efficiency of the Rail Track Buckling Risk Assessment (RW-KPI-5.3)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve at least 25% shorter duration and length of train speed slow orders that will be enabled by ordering of reducing the speed only in the hazardous rail areas predicted by the rail track buckling risk assessor.
- **Measurement Methodology:** The accuracy will be measured by comparing duration and length of train speed slow orders based on the rail track buckling risk assessed using the rail track buckling risk assessor, and current procedures used by railroad authorities, for a certain period of time.
- **Method:** Train speed slow orders will only apply to hazardous rail areas predicted by the rail track buckling risk assessor.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be assessed during Prototype Development, Pilot Deployment, and Real-Life Testing stages.

User Satisfaction (RW-KPI-5.3)

- **Target/Goal:** Attain high satisfaction ratings from end-users.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Collect feedback through surveys and interviews, then analyse user satisfaction scores and comments.
- **Method:** User satisfaction will be evaluated by collecting feedback through surveys and interviews.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** This KPI will be assessed during Feedback Collection and Final Evaluation stages.

3.7.6 Quality Control and Threshold Exceedance Monitoring

The Quality Control and Threshold Exceedance Monitoring component is designed to assess data

quality, monitor RTT against predefined thresholds, and detect anomalies in both incoming and internally generated data. Its primary goals are to ensure data reliability, enable early detection of critical conditions, and support proactive maintenance and safety measures in railway operations.

Objectives:

- Assess the quality of incoming data based on predefined metrics.
- Continuously compare predicted RTT values against established thresholds.
- Implement anomaly detection algorithms to identify unusual patterns or outliers.
- Process and analyse data in near real-time, with a maximum delay of 1 minute.

3.7.6.1 KPIs for Quality Control and Threshold Exceedance Monitoring

Data Quality Assessment Accuracy (RW-KPI-6.1)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve >90% accuracy in data quality assessment against predefined metrics.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Compare automated quality assessment results with manual verified evaluations on a diverse set of test data.
- **Method:** Statistical analysis
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

Anomaly Detection Precision (RW-KPI-6.2)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve >95% precision in identifying anomalies and outliers in RTT data.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Calculate precision using a labelled dataset of known anomalies and normal data points.
- **Method:** Unit testing of detecting accuracy.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing, Data Analysis

Time Behaviour - Threshold Exceedance Detection Timeliness (RW-KPI-6.3)

- **Target/Goal:** Detect and report threshold exceedances within 30 seconds of occurrence.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Measure the time difference between the timestamp of a threshold exceedance event and the timestamp of its detection and reporting.
- **Method:** Performance Testing
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing

Time Behaviour – Data Analysis Time (RW-KPI-6.4)

- **Target/Goal:** Complete data processing and analysis within 1 minute of data receipt for >95% of cases.

- **Measurement Methodology:** Track processing times for each data batch and calculate the percentage of cases meeting the 1-minute threshold.
- **Method:** Performance testing and statistical analysis
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing, Data Analysis

3.7.7 RWP Monitoring Application (WebGUI)

The WebGUI component is designed to provide a user-friendly, web-based interface for interacting with the rail track temperature monitoring system. It aims to offer intuitive access to data visualization, task management, and system configuration. The primary goals of the WebGUI are to enable users to efficiently manage RTBR tasks, visualize temperature data, and receive timely notifications.

Objectives

- Provide a responsive, web-based interface accessible across various devices and browsers.
- Enable user authentication and secure access to system features.
- Allow creation, management, and visualization of RTBR tasks and associated data.
- Support user data management, including upload and integration of vector data.
- Deliver timely notifications and alerts to users.
- Ensure high performance and availability for a smooth user experience.

3.7.7.1 KPIs for RWP Monitoring Application (WebGUI)

Functionality Accuracy (RW-KPI-7.1)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve > 95% accuracy in processing and responding to user requests.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Compare the application's responses to user requests with predefined expected outcomes.
- **Method:** Functional testing of various user requests and responses.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

User Data Management (RW-KPI-7.2)

- **Target/Goal:** Ensure >95% success rate for user data operations (upload, browse, select, download, delete).
- **Measurement Methodology:** Track successful completion of user data management tasks.
- **Method:** Usability testing of diverse user data operations requests.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

RTBR Task Management (RW-KPI-7.3)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve 99% accuracy in RTBR task CRUD (Creation, Read, Update, Delete) operations.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Track successful completion of RTBR task CRUD operations.
- **Method:** Unit testing of diverse RTBR task CRUD operations requests.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

User Satisfaction - Data Visualization and Analysis (RW-KPI-7.4)

- **Target/Goal:** Attain 90% user satisfaction with data visualization and analysis features.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Collect user feedback on visualization quality and analysis tools through user surveys and interviews.
- **Method:** Usability testing, user feedback collection and analysis.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing, Feedback Collection, Final Evaluation

User Satisfaction -Alerts (RW-KPI-7.5)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve 90% user satisfaction with the notification system.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Collect feedback on the usefulness and timeliness of alerts through surveys and interviews.
- **Method:** Usability testing, user feedback collection and analysis.
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Feedback Collection, Final Evaluation

User Interface Usability (RW-KPI-7.6)

- **Target/Goal:** Attain a high usability rating from end users.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Collect user feedback on WebGUI ease of use, navigation, and overall experience through surveys and usability testing.
- **Method:** Usability testing sessions and user surveys
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Prototype Development, Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing, Feedback collection, Final Evaluation

Time Behaviour (RW-KPI-7.7)

- **Target/Goal:** Maintain main interface load time under 2 seconds.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Monitor and record load times of the main interface.
- **Method:** Performance testing
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

System Availability (RW-KPI-7.8)

- **Target/Goal:** Achieve 99% system uptime.
- **Measurement Methodology:** Track system uptime and downtime periods.

- **Method:** Performance testing
- **Assessment Stage(s):** Lab Testing, Pilot Deployment, Real-Life Testing.

3.7.8 RWP pilot deployment

The SPARTA RWP pilot will be deployed on several sites that are managed by Serbian Railways Infrastructure (SRI) in order to get data necessary for service development as well as to evaluate pilot against defined KPIs.

The first deploying site is railroad Niš – Prahovo harbour (on Danube River), with a total length of section of 180,5 km (Figure 7). Although most parts of the track are reconstructed in the previous three years, some portions of the track are in very bad shape due to long periods without reconstruction (since 1961) and poor maintenance, which enable to assess pilot performance in the worst possible track condition. The track the section between Niš and Zaječar has more than 60 curves with a radius of 240 – 250 m which makes them prone to buckling. The track also passes across various landscapes with lot of vegetation as well as gorge and open terrain.

Figure 7. Track Niš – Prahovo

The second deploying site is railroad Niš – Preševo towards the North Macedonia boarder, with a

total length of section of 140 km and designed speed of 120 km/h (Figure 8). The track is a part of Pan European corridor X to Thessaloniki, Greece. The part of noted track is currently under reconstruction, with a completely new rail section between Niš and Brestovac with a length of 22.8 km. The section between stations Vladicin Han and Presevo, with length of 67 km is reconstructed some 10 years ago. The mentioned railroad is a particularly challenging corridor due to numerous small radius curves in Grdelica gorge (30 km length of the track trough the gorge) historically prone to buckling during hot weather.

Figure 8. Track Niš – Preševo

The third pilot deployment site is railroad Niš – Dimitrovgrad towards the border between Serbia and Bulgaria (Figure 9) in length of 97km with maximal train speed of 120 km/h. The railway line connecting Niš with Dimitrovgrad and the Bulgarian border is the branch Xc of the SEETO Corridor X. The line is part of the corridor connecting Central Europe to Bulgaria and Turkey through Croatia and Serbia. The track is currently under full reconstruction so there are sections which are completely new as well as sections which are in bad shape. The non reconstructed parts are historically prone to buckling due to small radius of curves and passage through rocky terrain with

high environmental temperatures during the summer months.

Figure 9. Track Niš – Dimitrovgrad

All possible test sites are selected because they are suitable for evaluation of SPATRA rail pilot demonstrator in various conditions. All possible test sites are characterised with existence of sections exposed to the sun for the whole day, as well as with shaded parts and parts which pass through gorges with very high environmental temperatures. As already noted, parts of sections are in very bad shape due to poor maintenance, and they have historically been prone to buckling. Final choice of the locations for final demonstration will be done based on their “availability” and permission to be issued by Serbian Railway Infrastructure. “Availability” would mean that the parts of the pilot deployment sites are under reconstructions/closed for regular traffic/low-exposed to traffic.

3.7.9 Pilot deployment scenario

Measurements will be continuously collected on the rail pilot deployment sites over a period of time that covers different weather conditions including very hot months (mainly May, June, July, and August). During rail pilot system development there will be 27 data acquisition sites in total, representing a combination of three different environmental conditions (direct sun, gorge, half shadow (forest)), three different rail track conditions (new, reconstructed, and old), and three different rail track curvatures (Figure 10). Two identical measuring stations (in situ sensors), which include rail temperature sensor, rail lateral displacement sensor and weather station will be used to gather data for pilot development as for actual pilot demonstration. The unmanned aerial vehicle with thermal camera will be used for validation during development and in final pilot demonstration (Figure 10). The in-situ system is currently tested in a lab environment and will be placed in

operational environment in November 2024.

Figure 10. Railway pilot (RWP) scenario

The schematic of the proposed in situ system for data acquisition, transmission, storage and retrieval is given in Figure 11, as already given in the updated version of Deliverable D2.1. Rail temperature and rail lateral displacement sensor data, along with weather data (atmospheric temperature, atmospheric humidity, atmospheric pressure, wind speed, wind direction, solar radiation, illuminance, dust concentration, and precipitation), will be monitored using two identical measurement systems throughout prespecified period of time on test rail sites with different characteristics (rail track condition, rail track curvature and environmental conditions). The empirical data will be acquired by outdoor waterproof wireless IOT Gateway and transmitted via 4G network to SPATRA cloud.

Figure 11. Schematics of in-situ sensor connection for the SPATRA RWP service

SPATRA cloud contains data repository for storing rail temperature, rail lateral displacement and weather data, as well as for storing EO data such as Sentinel-3 LST or Meteosat Second Generation (MSG) LST and available weather data. Schematics of the integrated system for data acquisition, transmission, storage and retrieval are given and described in the latest submitted version of SPATRA D2.1.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable D4.1 sets-up the basis for SPATRA pilots' demonstration and evaluation activities that will be conducted within WP4 tasks as it presents plans for both pilots, Road Infrastructure Monitoring Pilot (RDP) and Railway Monitoring and Prediction of Rail Temperature Zones Pilot (RWP), as well as it specifies the evaluation protocols and related KPIs according to which pilots will be evaluated in relevant environments.

This deliverable D4.1 reports the work done in SPATRA Task 4.1- Specification of the use cases for testing and validation methodology as well as the work done in Task4.2- Configure and establish SPATRA pilots, which refers to the design of a comprehensive configuration process to establish SPATRA pilots. This design ensures that the pilots will be configured correctly and will operate effectively. As such, this deliverable D4.1 sets-up the basis for further WP4 tasks, implementation of SPATRA pilots, integration and validation of modules, and execution of the pilots as well as the analysis of the results. These tasks and corresponding results will be reported in following two deliverables of WP4, D4.2- Integration and Validation Report (M22) and D4.3- Pilot Results and Analysis Report (M24).

5 REFERENCES

1. O'Brien, H. L., Cairns, P., & Hall, M. (2018). A practical approach to measuring user engagement with the refined user engagement scale (UES) and new UES short form. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 112, 28-39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2018.01.004>.